

Factorials, Integers, Binomial Coefficient and Factorial Theorem

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper presents a factorial theorem using factorial functions, integers, and binomial coefficients. This idea will help to researchers working in combinatorics, computation, science and engineering.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10

Keywords: algorithm, combinatorics, factorial, computation

1. Introduction

Combinatorial techniques [1-4] are used as powerful tools in artificial intelligence and machine learning for data analysis and cybersecurity for protection of the computing systems, devices, networks, programs and data from cyber-attacks. Also, the nonnegative integers play a crucial role in factorial functions or factorials for building the factorial theorems [1, 2] using binomial coefficients [3, 4].

2. Theorems in Factorials

The factorial of a non-negative integer n , denoted by $n!$, is the product of all positive integers less than or equal to n .

For example, $5! = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 4 \times 5 = 120$. Note that zero factorial is always one, that is, $0! = 1$.

Theorem : $(p^n)! = I_n \times (p!)^n$, where $n, I_n \geq 1; p \geq 0$ & n, p, I_n are integers.

Proof. $\binom{p+q}{p} = \frac{(p+q)!}{p!q!} = I$, where $I \geq 1$ & I is an integer.

$(p+q)! = I \times p!q! \Rightarrow (p \times q)! = I_1 \times p!q!$ since $(p \times q)! \geq (p+q)!$.

Let $q = p$. Then $(p \times p)! = I_2 \times p!p! \Rightarrow (p^2)! = I_2 \times (p!)^2$.

$(p^3)! = I_3 \times (p!)^3$. Here, $(p^2)! \geq (p!)^2 \Rightarrow (p^3)! \geq (p!)^3$, where $p \geq 0$ & p is an integer.

$(p^{n-1})! = I_{n-1} \times (p!)^{n-1} \Rightarrow (p^n)! = I_n \times (p!)^n$, where $n \geq 1; p \geq 0$ & n, p are integers.

Hence, theorem is proved.

3. Conclusion

In this article, a factorial theorem [1, 2] has been introduced using factorials, integers, and binomial coefficients. This idea refers to a methodological advance which is useful for

researchers working in computer science, computational science, and engineering to solve the real life problems.

References

- [2] Annamalai, C. (2022) Factorials and Integers for Applications in Computing and Cryptography. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2022) Application of Factorial and Binomial identities in Computing and Cybersecurit. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1666072/v2>.
- [3] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and its Applications. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-pnx53-v22>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computing Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Expansion. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4168016>.